

INSTITUTIONAL STRUCTURES IN ART SYSTEMS: OTHER NARRATIVES

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ABSTRACT

In this text, we propose an analysis of the “Oficina Escobar” project implemented since 2020, in the Missões Region - inland Rio Grande do Sul - based on theoretical references related to new institutionalities (CANCLINI, 2023) and, considering the activities developed in its work process, as a possible experience of institutional criticism (FRASER, 2020), highlighting mainly its implications in relation to collaborative practices (SCHOLETTE, BULHÕES, 2022) and the activities developed outside the scope of the centrality of the established art system.

Keywords: Oficina Escobar; art system; institutional critique; collaborative practices; dark energy

System discussed in historical context.

Art systems, whether international *mainstream* or local ecosystems, do not function autonomously or independently. They are always embedded in and articulated within historical contextual realities from which they draw inspiration and where they exert influence, either reaffirming established conditions or questioning them and constructing new alternatives. In this sense, the proliferation of analyses that address art systems in isolation, as if they were closed in on themselves, ignoring the complex social, political, and economic relationships in which they are articulated and the numerous consequences of these conditions and how they actively interfere with them, is quite concerning.

Thinking about institutional frameworks within an art system presupposes revisiting the history and current conditions of the disputes that unfold within it. Thus, Nestor Garcia Canclini (2023), in recent research, dedicated himself to observing how the relationships between institutions, artists, cultural workers, and audiences are transforming in the era of digital networks. With his research group, the author documents the precarization of institutions in the cultural field in the face of the neoliberal project of reducing state action and the growth and importance of digital platforms and applications, addressing the conditions during and after the pandemic, and questioning how to remake institutions. Revisiting the very concept of institutions, they point to new institutional frameworks, closely connected to communities and articulated in hybrid models (physical/digital).

Based on these contextual analyses and anchored in local issues, we propose to address the installation and development of the institutional experience of the *Escobar Workshop*, in the city of Entre-Ijuís, in the interior of Rio Grande do Sul. Initially created from the return of the artist Daniel Escobar to his place of origin during the Covid-19 pandemic, the space was enthusiastically received by the local community, which found in it a kind of historical museum, previously nonexistent in the city. Thus, it can be said that the Escobar Workshop project became a local institution, which articulates itself to the art system based on the artist's connections^{and} which he seeks to activate through online contacts during the pandemic. Perhaps in other times, without the resources of the connection networks made possible by the internet, which articulate all the activities developed there to different circuits of contemporary art, the project could not function.

Based on these basic assumptions, we propose a review of the trajectory of this experience, which began in 2020 and is becoming increasingly institutionalized. We intend to question the limits and possibilities of these processes in a place entirely outside the traditionally recognized art system and the more established cultural centers. In this analysis, we highlight the possibilities that are opening up in the artistic field for locations further from major centers in times of digital network dominance, as Canclini points out.

The Escobar Workshop is part of a group of movements that have emerged strongly in recent years in different regions of the country, revealing other possibilities for working in the artistic field that move away from the physical centrality of large metropolises. These initiatives are generally led by individuals who have had contact with the *mainstream art system* and who, due to various circumstances, have chosen to establish themselves on the margins, geographically speaking, developing more collaborative and participatory experiences with local communities. However, they maintain various links with institutions and other actors in

the art system, thus ensuring the reference to "art" in their work. The current development of online communication is a fundamental element of these experiences, most of them maintaining social networks and websites as a way to ensure visibility in the art field.

What is interesting to highlight is that in these new spaces, we generally find productions connected to contemporary art, taking place in locations that have not dealt with the traditions of academic or modern art. Since the artistic references of these communities are generally limited to the few inhabitants who have had the opportunity for training or museum visits, a new dynamic is established in the experiences of art that, from its origin, is based on the more flexible, inclusive, and experiential assumptions of contemporary artistic practices.

The art system and its boundaries.

Escobar Workshop is located in the city of Entre-Ijuís, an essentially agricultural center with approximately 8,000 inhabitants, which developed from the Ijuí River crossing, a link between the Guarani Jesuit reductions of São João Batista and Santo Ângelo, in what is now the state of Rio Grande do Sul. The city maintains its legacy as a bridge between places, with its central area currently crossed by a major highway (RS-344). The municipality holds a prominent position on the Missions Route, housing within its territory the São João Batista Archaeological Site, which was part of the Seven Peoples of the Missions (located 19km from the city center). It also integrates one of the main historical and cultural corridors in the world, connecting with Argentina and Paraguay through the Iguassu-Misiones route. This past is a source of pride for the city, lived in a patriotic way; few question its historical developments or critically address its contradictions and contemporary repercussions. Almost nothing is said about the massacre of the indigenous populations who lived there, and whose descendants, the survivors, are now undervalued in various ways, constituting the poorly paid workforce of the region.

In our analysis, we consider the artist as a bearer of the art system in his movements to other territories, since his *habitus*, ^{practices}, and narratives embody the values and legitimacy he has received socially. Reinforcing ties with his context, Escobar began to develop a personal work that strategically presupposes involvement with local communities, while simultaneously being committed to the values and criteria of contemporary art, something totally unknown to almost all of its inhabitants.

As a result, after 20 years of being closed, a warehouse located in the city center, which had previously housed two generations of family workshops (grandfather a

goldsmith/watchmaker and father a mechanic), underwent renovations to house the artist's studio, a library focused on visual arts, infrastructure for small exhibitions, art workshops, and facade interventions. In 2021, with funding from the Aldir Blanc Law, Oficina Escobar held its first cycle of public activities, including an exhibition, an urban intervention, the production of a mini-documentary, and the publication of a book. In this context, the old warehouse gained a luminous sign with its name, reactivating the memory of the place and the different trades it once housed, while simultaneously embracing its new function as a contemporary art studio. The intervention gives the place a new meaning, resuming its memories and updating it with a neon design and lighting.

Image 1: Daniel Escobar. *Escobar Workshop* , 2021. Acrylic, metal and LED lighting. Photography by Anderson Astor.

Continuing his project, Escobar produced an exhibition-installation based on objects he found on the site throughout the renovation period, titled "A Thousand and One Secrets of Workshops." The work includes the public opening of the artist's studio, where a collection of objects and documents dating back to the two previous generations of this workshop space was also installed. The exhibition/installation was received as a museum, due to the dynamics of its relationship with memory and, possibly, because the city's residents recognized the new space within a traditional conception of collection. We believe it is possible to consider, based on Canclini's analyses of new institutionalities, the workshop as a place that escapes already practiced models, breaking with established institutional dynamics.

IMAGE 2: Daniel Escobar. *A Thousand and One Secrets of Workshops*, 2021. Objects, tools, furniture, and documents installed in the artist's studio. Photography by Anderson Astor.

Operating in a geographically peripheral area in relation to major centers, the resources of networked communication have been fundamental to the existence of this project, both in terms of contacts with artists and other institutions, and in maintaining active social networks. In this sense, a distinguishing feature of this space has been the use, mainly of Instagram, to showcase work processes, as well as calls to the community to participate in each of the events promoted. The residencies, without concern for products as results, document all steps of the activities, exploring involvement in the creative procedures.

Collaborative practices explore possibilities and expand concepts.

As an extension of his work, and reinforcing ties with his context, the artist, in 2023, began developing a project for artist residencies that presupposes the involvement of residents with local communities in co-participatory works. The “Moving House Residency” is a program focused on artistic processes permeable to context and direct exchanges between artists and the community. The project has yielded a network of contacts with public schools in the city and region, where the artist identified potential for the development of artistic proposals that could be directly linked to the field of education. Artists are invited or selected through an open call to propose projects that involve conducting workshops with school groups in the region. Beyond residencies, the program also includes the production of books, documentaries, and exhibitions, having hosted seven residents from different regions of the country to date.

Considering its location outside the central urban areas where the art system is

established, and the community engagement the project fosters—capturing city residents in their relationships with the new institution, broadening their experiences and diversifying their perspectives—Oficina Escobar brings contemporary art to a community without prior experience with art, involving it in collaborative practices. Thus, we can think of it as a form of “dark energy of art.”

...I would like to propose the use of the concept of “dark energy,” which I adopted from reading the publications of Gregory Sholette. This author makes an analogy to the studies of cosmic sciences, using the term “dark matter” to address a force composed of invisible and unknown elements, responsible for bringing together the artistic field. According to him, many unknown and invisible actors, to the superficial gaze of those who only focus their studies on the *mainstream*, are important factors in the aggregation and maintenance of the functioning of art. For the author, they constitute the “dark matter of art.”

However, considering what the cosmic sciences indicate I think that in this case Sholette should have used the concept of “dark energy,” since he focuses his attention mainly on the counter-hegemonic actions that artists and groups develop in a more or less anonymous way. Analogously, in my view, they are closer to this second invisible force that acts in the cosmos, as the force of change that, by causing alterations in the universe, promotes its continuous expansion. Although they cannot be seen, both dark matter and dark energy have been theorized and considered vitally important in the dynamics of galaxy cohesion and the expansion of the universe. (BULHÔES, pg 17, 2022).

In its pilot edition in 2023, the Casa Movente Residency project was funded by the FAC Visual grant from Sedac-RS and took as its starting point the history and vocation of the Oficina itself, which also houses a collection of objects produced by the artist's grandfather during his last years. The first resident artist was Manoela Furtado (Porto Alegre), who incorporated Oficina Escobar as a research territory, seeking “*Found and Kept*” as a strategy for resignifying everyday spaces and objects, and carrying out artistic experiments in the field of photo-performance with school groups. The basement of the old house, which was once a workshop for repairing objects or building new ones from residual materials, temporarily became a workshop for imagining new uses and reinventing ways of relating to space and objects. In a video performance, the artist reacts to a place that is constructed from noises, wear and tear, residues, and memories.

IMAGE 3: Manoela Furtado, 2023. *When chairs wear shoes, I dress in love*. Video performance. Photography by André Netto.

Also in this first edition, the artist Efe Godoy (Belo Horizonte) explored the extensive backyard that extends to the back of the warehouse as a space of multiple discoveries, documenting plants, insects, gates, and other elements of this landscape through drawings and watercolors. The artist, who also works with mural paintings in different cities, used the warehouse facade as a support for an intervention, expanding forms of interaction with the community and making evident the desire to reveal what is hidden through the phrase "backyard, an outside inside" that composes the painting. The booklet workshop *Para Fabular Quintais (To Create Fabulous Backyards)*, a methodology developed by the artist in collaboration with public schools in Entre-Ijuís, was later carried out in different Brazilian institutions such as Inhotim, Casa Fiat de Cultura, and Sesc São Paulo.

Movements that incorporate the territory

The second edition of the "Casa Movente Residency," in 2025, resumes funding from the Aldir Blanc National Policy, now based on a specific call for proposals for Visual Arts within a modality intended for spaces with systematic programming, and takes as its conceptual axis the city of Entre-Ijuís itself, in its relationship with the context of the Missions. A book organized in 1991 as a didactic tool for elementary school, "*Conhecendo Entre-Ijuís*" (*Getting to Know Entre-Ijuís*), is the starting point for Daniel Escobar's curatorial project, who first encountered the publication at the age of 8. About 30 years later, perceiving the need to construct new narratives about the place, the title of this book is recontextualized, ceasing to

allude to an instrument that presents and defines the city to become an invitation to experience and explore its territory. If in the past a group of teachers was responsible for systematizing information in a textbook that made it possible for children and adolescents to understand the historical and geographical aspects of the city, the methodology adopted here places artists, teachers, and students as active agents in the construction of new coordinates, so that the city can be thought of based on a collective, diverse, sensitive, and vibrant approach.

The stays began with the artist Tuane Eggers (Porto Alegre), who conducted research based on the lichen formations that developed on the ruins of the Guarani Jesuit Reduction of São João Batista. Reflecting on the numerous possible narratives about this territory and paying attention to the life forms that emerge from what can also be considered ruins, the artist created a kind of cabinet of curiosities in her studio. Her workshop, "Contemplating the Tiny Greatness," conducted in collaboration with biologist Beto Mohr, invited students from a rural school located near the archaeological site to map the small organisms of this territory together, using macro lenses attached to the students' and teachers' cell phones. Eggers proposes a reflection on the role of art as a tool for translation, propagation, and affective recovery of the relationship with other living beings. It is important to highlight that the artist's stay in the Missions also included the participation of her family, an important condition for her participation in this edition of the program, and one that was very positively received by Oficina Escobar. Beto Mohr and little Flora (2 years old) were essential to the work developed during the residency.

The second edition of the project also featured a new element: the selection of an artist through a national call for entries, expanding the program's visibility and mapping more than 150 proposals from artists who expressed intentions to work based on this territory. The selected artist was Laryssa Machada (Rio de Janeiro), who artistically and imagistically investigated the construction of a fiction about Brazil. In the context of the Missions, the artist developed the series " *Power of Fire*," where she is photographed as a warrior on horseback, with the ruined cathedral at the São Miguel Arcanjo archaeological site in the background. The scene ignites iconographies of resistance based on records of Charrúa warriors, made by Debret in the 18th century, embodied as gestures by the artist. Her images intertwine with the missionary territory, adopting the ruins as a backdrop for a warrior who ignites time and space, and dresses in the remnants of working the land, in a region dominated by agribusiness. Her research created an intertwining with different agents for the production of the photographs, involving everything from local businesses, which collaborated in the production of costumes made from repurposed agricultural packaging, to the participation of local photographers and a horse trainer who

provided the artist with tools and accompanied the development of her performance for the photograph. In her interaction with school groups, the artist developed, in a collective setting, a practice that is common to her creative work: the construction of costumes with recyclable or residual materials imbued with their own meaning.

IMAGE 4: Laryssa Machada, 2025. *Firepower*. Photography by Thiago Mann.

The third artist-in-residence in 2025 was Claudia Hamerski (Porto Alegre). Her work is based on the practice of drawing and also on the waste generated by the process, with themes that reveal nature's insubordination to the architecturally established. During the residency, she established a dynamic she called "*from line to territory*," inviting the local community to investigate, through the language of drawing, at the São João Batista Archaeological Site, the lines, textures, colors, and shadows present in elements of the vegetation. In this interaction, she became interested in the Umbu tree, a centuries-old tree that grows on the ruins of the Guarani civilization, especially a specimen that survived the test of time, adapting and being shaped by events over the years. The tree, with its trunk invaded by construction ruins and its roots perforated by excavations, is also resistance and ruin, a historical mark of the actions of time and man.

Also this year, Paulo Nazareth (Minas Gerais) inaugurated, during his stay, the first museum in the city of Entre-Ijuís: MAMA (Monument to the Mother of the World). A process-oriented work by the artist, he invites people from all over the world to draw the mother they carry in their memory, interacting with the work as it is created, in a joint action between the artist and the participants. An act of homage and sharing, a space to draw, write, remember, create. A collective archive, simultaneously intimate and political, in homage to mothers – all

mothers – and to the gesture of teaching, caring, narrating, sharing. The work connects Nazareth's experience in Entre-Ijuís with other points on the globe, based on a collection that is being expanded and moved from the nomadic perspective that defines the poetics (and life) of the artist. The MAMA project has already been installed in locations such as FAE-UFMG (Belo Horizonte), the Tamayo Museum (Mexico), John Jay College (USA), and the Mendes Wood DM Gallery (São Paulo). Tapioca biscuits were produced during the event and offered to the public by the artist, a recipe from his mother and also a memory that materializes through aromas and flavors. The artist's work in Entre-Ijuís also presented a new project by Nazareth, the CEEJA - Center for Studies and Experiments with Autonomous Gardens. Installed in the courtyard as an annex to the workshop, the space was composed of a wide variety of seedlings and seeds of plants with yellow flowers or fruits available in the region, gardening equipment, soil, organic fertilizers, and pots, which were made available for community interaction. The CEEJA also originated the creation of a garden in a public school in the city, where students chose a "gift word" to be drawn with yellow flower seedlings in a collective action carried out in the school playground. The word "Nostalgia," chosen by the students, was planted in an area of the backyard visible from the street, as a way of offering it as a gift to the community.

IMAGE 5: Paulo Nazareth, 2025. *CEEJA Center for Study and Experiments with Autonomous Gardens*. Gardening workshop at EE Dr. Carlos Kruel. Photography by Thiago Mann.

In its emerging institutional action in the city, the Escobar Workshop takes into account actions embedded in the context of institutional critique, ⁵ insofar as it positions itself as an art institution while simultaneously questioning the traditional assumptions of these practices. Thus, the proposals developed by the residents, chosen within the conceptual project

of the artist Daniel Escobar, fit within the premises of institutional critique. According to scholars (FRASER, MTL COLLECTIVE), institutional critique has sought an evolution from internal critical positions to more radical actions in social terms, expanding its relations with the systemic practices of established institutions. Most artists recognize that they are always within the art system, even when it is questioned. This is the case with the dynamics established in the relationships of the activities carried out, with the city of Entre-Ijuís, its territory, its history, its current reality, and with the community, which strengthen the critical aspects of the action of this new institutionality of the local space, rethinking established narratives and enabling approaches that incorporate new actors into the heritage issue.

Students from a rural school located near the archaeological site continuously followed the work, developing activities with all the residents of the year. Focused on both micro and macro levels, the project involves local agents who enter the field of contemporary art and provide tools for the artists in their explorations of the city and region. At the micro level, there is an exploration of the local environment, perspectives that perceive other realities in the immediate habitat and its surroundings; at the macro level, it critically addresses the history of the region, its traditions, and its contemporary developments. The Workshop project, among its multiple activities, includes a book and a documentary featuring the artists and the communities involved in the production of the works. An exhibition with the group of residents will be displayed at the Historical Museum of the Missions, located in the city of Santo Ângelo (capital of the Missions), with a confirmed tour to the city of Porto Alegre in early 2026, the year that will be dedicated to the extensive celebration of the 400th anniversary of the Missions in Rio Grande do Sul.

Final considerations

We can consider the Escobar Workshop as an already consolidated project that is considerably modifying the cultural landscape of the city and even the region. The current funding through the Aldir Blanc National Policy, which in 2021 gave rise to its public program amidst the Covid-19 pandemic, raises again the debate about a certain systematization of the decentralization of resources for culture in the country (CANCLINI, 2023), also allowing for reflection on other public policies that act in this sense, such as the Points of Culture. The focus on the city and the region ends up bringing to light the context in which the project is inserted, addressing more emphatically the history of the social formation of the region, whose colonization was marked by successive territorial disputes that decimated the original

indigenous communities.

Furthermore, its dissemination and integration into the art system, both by contemporary artists and art critics, reinforces the phenomenon pointed out at the beginning of this text and highlights its presence as a factor in the expansion of the art system, traditionally restricted to large urban and geopolitical centers. Thus, this type of proposal can be considered a "dark energy," insofar as it expands the art system in territorial terms, encompassing locations previously entirely outside the art circuits, reinforcing the idea that artists carry the art system with them in their travels. Even more importantly, it is necessary to consider the expansion in terms of new aesthetic, methodological, and conceptual possibilities, since participating artists feel challenged and stimulated to carry out experiments that they might not dare to execute in traditional art spaces, where they are more committed to the results and repercussions of their work.

The focus of Oficina Escobar's activities on the dynamics of contemporary art, with collaborative practices involving the local community in different sectors and aspects, reinforces its analysis within the conceptual issues addressed in this text.

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Notes

¹ As part of the development of his participation as Holder of the Olavo Setúbal Chair, at the Institute of Advanced Studies of USP, in 2020/2021.

² Daniel Escobar has a prior connection with the art system, with university training in visual arts, participating in residencies, contemporary art fairs, and exhibitions in museums and galleries in Brazil and abroad.

³ Considering here the concept of Pierre Bourdieu presented in the book *The Economy of Symbolic Exchanges*.

⁴ The cosmic sciences work with two forces that, although theorized, have not yet been visualized: dark matter and dark energy. According to these studies, they have different actions, with the first being responsible for the cohesion of galaxies and the second for the expansion of the universe. The basic characteristic of dark matter in cosmology is its aggregating factor, functioning in a centripetal and agglutinating way and, even though it cannot be seen, it is responsible for the cohesion of galaxies, maintaining planets and other celestial bodies in harmonious coexistence. Dark energy, in contrast, promotes the discontinuity of the universe, ensuring its permanent expansion.

⁵ Primarily because in his personal work the artist has always been involved with institutional criticism, as can be seen in his master's thesis.